

Research-In-Progress Paper

Towards accelerating restorative transitions in urban, peri-urban, and urban-rural environments - everybody onboard through the new generation of living labs

Maximising synergies and managing trade-offs depend on specific practices, scale of implementation, governance, capacity building, integration with existing land use and the involvement of local communities and Indigenous peoples and through benefit-sharing, supported by frameworks such as Land Degradation Neutrality within the UNCC

(IPCC Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022)

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Abstract

This paper explores the concept of transformative governance to foster individual and collective responsibility towards positive climate change. Anchored in the Anthropocene epoch, where human activities have a profound impact on the planet's systems, the study emphasises the dual capacity of humanity to both degrade and regenerate our environment. The framework of the triple transition—social, green and digital—is proposed as a comprehensive multi-faceted approach to navigate the complexity of current and future ecological and societal issues.

Central to this discourse are collaborative methodologies that include multi-actor and multi-level co-creation governance. These methodologies facilitate the creation of the next generation of living labs and ecosystems that drive social, digital and environmental systemic transformation.

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The paper underlines the importance of eco-systemic thinking, community-based actions and stakeholder engagement in fostering a people-centred approach to climate governance.

Through in-depth interviews to key stakeholders in regional innovation ecosystems in different world regions, the research deepens on effective strategies for aligned shared visions, decentralised governance and active citizen participation, including actors from the quadruple or n-helix.

The study demonstrates that leveraging the triple transition and collaborative methodologies within the new generation of T-Shaped living labs is essential for achieving sustainable and regenerative impacts in purpose-driven and future-ready resilient urban environments.

Key words

Co-Creation, Transformative governance, Quadruple helix, Systemic change, Common good, Triple transition (social, green and digital), Peri-urban transition

Introduction: Understanding the shared responsibility for an accelerated positive climate change in urban and peri-urban settlements

Climate transition should be a concern for everyone, regardless of the size or wealth of their city or community, i.e. large, influential cities, as well as smaller towns, villages, municipalities, peri-urban settlements, or communities. Humanity is in a state of transition, reflecting the broader shifts occurring on our planet in the Anthropocene era. This epoch is characterised by significant human impact on the Earth's geology and ecosystems, driven by anthropogenic changes. As illustrated in figure 1, 'we are all in the same boat', immersed in an environmental emergency and must work together to ensure our collective effort to prevent further damage on the planet.

Figure 1. 'We are all in the same boat,' Source: Eoh-for-Good®

We are continuously faced with transformations at various levels, from personal to global, despite an inherent resistance to change, evidenced by our tendency to react only when crises are imminent. Recent events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, severe droughts, drastic floods, wildfires, and social inequities exemplify the "heavy storms" that disrupt our socio-economic, political, and environmental status quo. Among the most pressing of these global challenges are the need to mitigate and adapt to climate change (Smith et al., 2020).

These disruptions highlight the need for a courageous acknowledgment of our role as predators or exploiters without measure or control, or as positive agents of change with the Anthropocene epoch presenting unique governance challenges and opportunities. Humanity has arrived now by prioritising individual interests, with only a few taking responsibility for the common good. We must promote shared visions and nurture new generations of change agents committed to collaborative and transformative governance by embracing this shared responsibility.

We urgently need a global and personal wake up to generate real transformations of our societies, our artificial systems, and our natural ecosystems for which we are responsible. We need to have “the courage to recognise that we, humans, are the agents of such changes, for bad or for good. Our choice is for good, for a new common good. We need shared visions about this goal; we need new generations of social, digital, and environmental innovators and entrepreneurs, committed to boost collaborations; we need to create new transformative governance, based on new methodologies, tools and services to respond to these changes” (Caro-Gonzalez, 2023).

This paper examines how new forms of collaborative transformative governance can promote individual and collective responsibility for positive climate action. We can address the unsustainable situation and strive for a fairer, inclusive and sustainable future for humanity to achieve meaningful societal, systemic and ecological transformations for the common good through the exploration and development of new methodologies, dynamics, tools and profiles that reflect on the past, analyse the present and anticipate the future (Jain, 2024; Caro-Gonzalez et al., 2023; El-Sherbini et al., 2024). The work deepens on the need to accelerate the social transition, integrating it with the green and digital transitions, the so-called triple transition (social, green, and digital). Innovation, industry-led efforts, digital leadership, individual and social conduct towards climate neutrality and regeneration must be rooted in responsible environmental engagement in urban and peri-urban settlements. The EU’s Roadmap acknowledges the need for changes in social habits and active participation in governance (European Union, 2022), with the 2022 IPCC report already highlighting multi-level governance as crucial for climate transition (Lwasa et al., 2022). However, the novelty of this study lies in placing individual and shared responsibility at the core of multi-level initiatives, making it the driving force behind sustainable change or transition. In other words, making responsibility a conscious effort is what can lead humanity to the success of these transitions.

Theoretical framework - Systemic approaches for fast-tracked positive environmental shifts in urban and peri-urban communities: triple transition, multi-level, and transformative governance

Urban areas play a critical role in mitigating climate change due to their significant greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, growing urban populations, expanding urban land and infrastructure and the long lifespans of buildings and transport systems (Seto et al., 2021). Efforts are already underway at the highest levels, as seen in climate summits and the 2030 Agenda, among other initiatives (European Commission, 2024; United Nations, 2024).

Systemic approaches to governance are crucial for a) promoting and accelerating regenerative climate change in urban, peri-urban, and urban-rural settlements; b) ensuring long-term stability; and c) supporting transformative actions that drive rapid positive environmental changes in these communities.

The **Triple Transition framework** (Caro-Gonzalez *et al.*, 2023) embodies a forward-looking vision that propels an encompassing complex transition: social, green, and digital, under the motto: “One for All, All for One” triple transition. The Triple Transition advocates for intertwined transitions that are just and human-centred and environmentally friendly, guided by the Sustainable Development Goals and context-driven agendas that defend the resolution of challenges identified by different communities (e.g. indigenous, minorities, etc.). It addresses the urgent need to transition from destructive patterns, such as warfare, environmental degradation, and social alienation, to regenerative practices (e.g. circular economy and sustainable and equitable growth, [Eoh-lution podcast #17](#)) to be translated into actionable policies and offer:

- a) a strong approach to achieving transformative governance by addressing these dimensions simultaneously;
- b) the promotion of a global dynamic reconfiguration by promoting multi-agent engagement to define new purposes and visions aligned with the SDGs and the global agenda, specifically climate change targets.
- c) a systemic approach centred on societal development vital for balancing economy and society in a sustainable way through the interaction of digital, energy and environmental concerns.
- d) a co-evolutionary process that embodies the “one for all, all for one” principle, directing humanity towards a life-sustaining purpose.

Cities and peri-urban areas are envisioned as vast “co-laboratories” (new generation of living labs and ecosystems) with capacity to drive radical changes through experimentation, learning and multi-actor engagement, promoting systemic innovation and collaboration across various dimensions (Scholl *et al.*, 2022; Bhatta *et al.*, 2023; Serra, Caro-Gonzalez and Colobrants, 2024). This ambitious vision aligns with European values and aims to achieve the targets of the United Nations 2030 Global Agenda.

To effectively address climate change in urban and peri-urban areas, it is essential to involve **multiple levels of governance**, including government and non-state entities and secure substantial funding beyond sector-specific strategies (Costero Bolaños, 2024; Melnykovich *et al.*, 2024; Cheshmehzangi, 2019). Multi-level governance coordinates policies across local, regional, national, and international levels, ensuring coherent and aligned efforts to respond comprehensively to complex challenges.

Authors like Kern wrote about the EU multilevel climate governance based on the dynamics between leaders, followers, and laggards. She stated that "upscaling of local experiments is not limited to horizontal upscaling between leading cities because the role of cities in EU climate governance has changed. Authority and competencies shifted not only upwards to the EU, but also downwards to subnational authorities." She explained that "local climate action has become an important feature of European climate governance, and a considerable percentage of Europeans now live in cities with relatively ambitious reduction goals. Although big, wealthy, and powerful cities, led by charismatic leaders, have become important players in climate governance, local climate action is not a panacea" (Kern, 2019).

Figure 2. Horizontal, vertical, and hierarchical upscaling in EU governance. Source: Kern, 2019.

Fuhr discussed the benefits of "bottom-up" approaches to climate change, stressing urban climate experimentation and its alignment with polycentric climate governance (Fuhr et al., 2018). Fuhr introduced "embedded upscaling," a governance mode that combines horizontal, vertical, and hierarchical arrangements and a model that considers the dynamics between leaders, followers, and laggards to create an integrated governance setting (Fuhr et al., 2018).

Transformative governance refers to the process of how societies are managed to achieve sustainable and equitable outcomes. It involves moving beyond traditional governance models to embrace more holistic, inclusive, and adaptive approaches for the common good. Key elements of transformative governance include:

- a) **Eco-systemic thinking** to understand and manage urban contexts in an integrated, holistic and planet friendly manner;

- b) **Community-based and citizen engagement** to actively involve local communities and individuals in decision-making processes ‘*we are all in the same boat*’ (figure 1) and have the responsibility to ‘add our drop in the ocean’;
- c) **Multi-actor engagement** to ensure that diverse perspectives and interests are represented and considered; and
- d) **Systems transformation** to promote comprehensive changes across social, economic, and environmental systems with a long-term common good vision.

Through the principles of transformative governance, it is possible to navigate the complexities of profound transitions and shape a more just, sustainable, and inclusive world for future generations. The critical challenge lies not in the availability of information, data, or knowledge—we possess abundant scientific and practical evidence of the detrimental impact we are having on the planet. Instead, **the focus must be on how to effectively implement this knowledge and regenerative oriented policies and practices.** For responding to this ‘how’: The role of social innovators is crucial in designing new frameworks that include not only political and religious leaders and entrepreneurs but also members of organised communities united by a common purpose. These social infrastructures not only implement but also sustain, refine, and redefine the process, ensuring its continuous development and success. This study explores how experts have designed specific strategies to make urban and peri-urban settlements consciously sustainable, drawing on the illustrative experiences and concrete cases discussed in the interviews.

Research methodology

This research adopts a rigorous qualitative methodology to investigate the opportunities and challenges associated with accelerating positive climate change in urban, peri-urban, and urban/rural settlements worldwide. The study examines initiatives of varying maturity across multiple regions, levels of actor engagement and thematic areas.

This study aims to capture rich narratives and gain in-depth insights into the dynamics and processes essential for transformative governance in urban environments conducive to positive climate change. Qualitative methods are well-suited for exploring complex social phenomena, as they provide rigorous scientific methods to delve into nuanced perspectives and the contextual factors shaping these multifaceted systems.

The study's sample design prioritises representativeness and diversity to encompass a wide array of perspectives and experiences from various initiatives across global regional ecosystems, including Europe, America, and Asia (and examples from Africa through the established cooperation of some experts). Purposeful and snowball sampling methods were employed to select participants and cases that align closely with the research

objectives. This approach ensures comprehensive insights into Innovation in governance through multi-level and multi-helix approaches, societal actor co-responsibility and the spaces and dynamics necessary for innovation to propel climate-positive transitions within the framework of a systemic triple transition.

The participant pool includes a diverse range of individuals, from young and experienced committed activists and professionals, providing a thorough view of the field. Purposeful and snowball sampling techniques facilitated the identification of relevant participants across different geographical locations, thematic focuses, stakeholder groups and levels of initiative maturity. This strategy ensures the sample reflects the heterogeneity of urban, peri-urban, and urban/rural settlements and mitigates biases.

The study conducted 17 semi-structured in-depth interviews with key stakeholders engaged in innovative collaborative initiatives, recognised as experienced or emerging leaders in transformative governance across urban, peri-urban, and rural-urban contexts. Selection criteria included geographical and diverse representativeness (including gender balance⁴ with 55,6% male and 44,4% female), initiative maturity, actor diversity and thematic breadth. This rigorous selection process ensures an in-depth understanding of the varied contexts and sectors involved. The table below summarises the sample, detailing the countries and areas of expertise, such as health, cultural and creative industries (CCIs), education, public policy and social movements advocating for the rights of women, youth, minorities, and disabled individuals. This overview underscores the diverse expressions of innovative transformative governance, co-responsibility and co-creation across different contexts and sectors, with a focus on identifying examples of positive or regenerative climate change practice.

The research also integrates findings from desk research to establish the state of the art and provide a foundation for discussion and analysis. This is further complemented by advanced keyword coding using Atlas.ti for detailed analysis. This methodological approach enables a detailed understanding of the current landscape and facilitates the identification of key themes and patterns relevant to positive climate change initiatives.

⁴ Note: This study acknowledges a non-binary perspective on gender. However, the sample does not include any LGBTQIA+ representatives among the interviewees.

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Table 1. List of semi-structured in-depth interviews conducted with key stakeholders (arranged alphabetically by country of initiative location)

Location (country/region)	Code	Scope	Gender	Fields	Target Groups
Belgium (Europe)	I4-BE	International	F	Education, inclusion, integrity, common language, social movements	Youth, academia
Chile (Latin America)	I2-CL	National	M	Technology Education, Social Sustainability	Society, academia, public policy makers
Denmark (Europe)	I11-DK	National	M	Techno-antropology, Fire and security technologies, Information and Communication Technologies (ICT), Policy development	Society, public administration
Estonia (Europe)	I3-EE	National	F	Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) Museums, Development, Intergenerational use of media, Digitalisation	Society, public administration and local culture preservation
Hamburg, GER (Europe)	I6-GER	Regional European	M	Economy, innovation, startups, advanced technology, health, civic engagement	Public administration, ministry, civil society
Japan (Asia)	I17 - JPN	National	F	Economy cooperation, Public administration	Public administration, OECD, academia,
Mexico (America)	I5-MX	National	M	Digitalisation, AI, technology, culture, language inclusion, innovation and indigenous practices	Indigenous communities, civil society
the Netherlands (Europe)	I10-NL	International	M	Ecosystem redesign, Blockchain technology	Business, academia, technology
Norway (Europe)	I9-NO	International	F	Sustainable innovation, Engineering, Education, Tech transfer, Gender, Health technology	Academia, women, society
Peru (Latin America)	I1-PE	National	F	Gender Intersectional approach, Entrustment of women	Women, Society
Poland (Europe)	I7-PL	European	M	Territorial development-rural/urban, civic participation and participatory practices, CCIs	Culture institution, civil society
Philippines (Asia)	I16- PHL	National	F	Education, youth engagement, and volunteer work: Society Helix	Non profit organizations, education
Spain, Catalonia (Europe)	I8-ES	Regional International	M	Helix participation, innovation universal systems, research and innovators, governance.	Innovation ecosystems, connection and collaboration helixes
Spain (Europe)	I12-ES	Regional	F	Integration, Diversity, Education	Civil society, territory balance, public administration
Spain (Europe)	I13-ES	National	M	Politics, re-urbanization of rural areas, Territorial and social innovation	Civil society, Public sector, government, Policy makers
Spain (Europe)	I15 - ES	International	M	Youth, civic, and non-political organizations dedicated to improving society: society helix.	Young activists and civic organizations
Switzerland (Europe)	I14-CH	International	M	Sustainable energy, electrification of transport, energy policy, urban regeneration, knowledge & technology transfer.	Researchers, policymakers, energy sector, sustainable technology experts.

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This study is part of a broader ongoing research project. The sample comprises representatives from Europe, Latin America, Asia, and Africa with the aim to examine context-driven urban and peri-urban climate change initiatives (e.g. community led, public policies, private-public collaborations) that seek for positive impact.

The sample for this study includes initiatives from 14 countries across Europe, Latin America, and Asia. These initiatives vary in scope, encompassing:

- **Living labs on circular economy** (e.g. Tokoro Lab, Japan)
- **Long-term institutional transformative plans** (e.g. Danish Institute for Fire and Security Technologies; Estonian National Museum; i2Cat Foundation; Norwegian University of Science and Technology);
- **Community-based projects** (Equipo Europa; Global Shapers to promote the engagement of young people),
- **European education, research, and innovation projects** (FORTH in Philippines; INTEGER in three European regions)
- **Social movements** (e.g. Xquenda_Lab in México for Zapoteca indigenous people; Mujeres Conectadas in Perú to enhance women participation in Trujillo region),
- **Local, regional, or national development strategies** (e.g. Commonwealth of Municipalities Alto Tajo, Spain; Catalanian regional strategy; Chilean national strategy for Social Sustainability),
- **European networks and Associations** (e.g. European Network of Living Labs - Working Group Energy & Environment; European Network of Cultural Centres; Education for and Interdependent World).

Most of the experts consulted possess extensive intercultural and international experience, with many having lived in multiple countries or settings. This diverse background allows them to offer a broad range of perspectives and insights.

The table provided details the country where each primary initiative is based. However, it is important to note that the interviews also cover other initiatives, whether past or ongoing, in separate locations.

Analysing the role of transformative governance in building resilient and regenerative urban and peri-urban settlements for accelerated climate transition

The urgent need of co-responsibility for accelerating regenerative urban and peri-urban settlements

This section addresses the complexity of urban systems and the need for a systemic approach that underscores holistic planning and systems thinking, especially in the context of the Anthropocene. It explores the balance between universal and singular, contextualised innovations, highlighting the role of multi-level governance in managing these dynamics. It also focuses on the enhancement of both individual and collective responsibility, highlighting the importance of co-creation as a key driver of innovation and sustainability. Furthermore, it underscores the critical role of active participation by diverse actors in the design, implementation, and evaluation of initiatives.

The complexity of urban systems requires a systemic approach, where **holistic planning and system thinking are crucial**. This approach adheres to the principle of 'all for one, one for all,' triple transition: social, green, and digital. This stresses that addressing climate change is not just an environmental issue but also an encompassing social and technological challenge.

Understanding multi-level governance which entails local/global, urban/rural, inter-regional within or across countries collaboration. This involves recognising a verticality and horizontality of actors, ranging from the most local to a broader scope, with each playing different roles in the process, tailored to institutional, regional, national, or international structures, dynamics, and purposes.

Concurrently, various authors (Di Gregorio et al., 2019; Gonzales-Iwanciw et al., 2020; Fuhr et al., 2018) have already discussed **multi-level governance**, as climate change governance has evolved into a complex polycentric structure spanning global, national, and sub-national levels, relying on both formal and informal networks and policy channels. This intricate governance framework involves state and non-state actors at various levels in formulating and implementing climate policies, reflecting the 'glocal' nature of climate change—where its impacts are locally distinct, yet solutions require multi-level governance. The global nature of climate change mitigation and the local nature of its impacts and adaptation pose specific multi-level governance challenges for policy integration. However, the cross-level interactions between mitigation and adaptation efforts remain underexplored; and social learning, defined as a convergent change in stakeholders' perspectives and understanding, is crucial in

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this context, as it fosters integrated solutions through collective support and concerted actions by multiple stakeholders. Studies highlight that effective climate change adaptation requires not only active participation from diverse stakeholders but also governance structures that facilitate learning and transformation. Social learning links to the resilience of socio-ecological systems, enabling stakeholders to foresee and adapt to changes, thus enhancing system resilience; while policy learning, another critical concept, involves states learning from experiences and modifying actions based on evaluations of previous policies. This process can lead to innovative policies or continuous refinements of existing ones.

As Heinen et al. (2022) affirm, polycentric climate governance and multi-level governance operate across five dimensions: governance issues, decision-makers, interactions, rules-in-use, and dependency degrees. Polycentric governance emphasises local self-regulation, while multi-level governance focuses on formally interdependent actors collaborating across government levels.

For example, in transnational municipal networks, cities operate under different rules based on national legal frameworks. Some cities engage in self-regulated climate actions, while others integrate efforts across government levels with substantial funding.

These differences lead researchers to varying conclusions on factors like leadership, trust, and self-regulation. Regarding cities, although cities like Copenhagen and Sydney take effective climate actions, many small to medium-sized ones lack appropriate strategies, highlighting the urgent need for proactive sub-national policies to limit global temperature rise to 1.5°C.

Agenda 2030 highlights the importance of multi-level adaptation governance, including non-state actors from civil society and the private sector. This implies the need for wider arenas of engagement for diverse actors to collectively solve problems and to unlock the synergies between adaptation and mitigation and sustainable development IPCC, 2022:111). (Pörtner et al., 2022)

Most mitigation practices can be implemented without competing for land and can offer multiple co-benefits. Additionally, some practices can reduce the need for land conversion, increasing the effectiveness of other measures in addressing climate change mitigation and adaptation, combating land degradation and desertification, and improving food security. Many of these practices also support sustainable development and other societal goals (Smith et al., 2020). To minimise maladaptation, multi-sectoral, multi-actor and inclusive planning with flexible pathways promotes low-

regret, timely actions. These actions keep options open, provide benefits across multiple sectors and systems and help define the available solution space for long-term climate change adaptation (IPCC, 2022).

Several experts, in line with the ideas of the Anthropocene, suggest that innovation processes have the potential to transform individuals and societies. One expert highlight that through these processes, individuals can undergo significant transformation.

'Subjects in one form can transform, or we can transform ourselves through these innovation processes. [Translated from Spanish] (I8-ES, 2024; 00:08:48).

Another (I8-ES, 2024; 00:26:11) stresses the concept of cultural innovation as a human-driven phenomenon, asserting that we are actively creating the world we inhabit. However, there is a need for a theory of cultural innovation that holds us accountable for the changes we instigate and those occurring in nature. This theory should reflect on our actions within both the human and artificial realms, recognising our responsibility as creators of the artefacts we produce. The expert notes a surprising lack of awareness among people regarding their role in this creative process and the impact it has on natural evolution. This is specially what the multi-level, multi-i model manages to solve.

Figure 3 'multi-level, multi-vertical and horizontal interconnected perspectives' presents a holistic approach where bottom-up, top-down and middle-ground perspectives converge, with the figure of a tornado pushing centripetal forces absorbing the innovation from the edges (Caro-Gonzalez, 2023). Busquets proposed the concept of Orchestrating Smart Business Networks (SBN) (Busquets, 2010), which complements the idea of the tornado. He analysed the network's centripetal and centrifugal forces to test the managerial functions to shape the structural dynamics of innovation. This managerial approach can create an efficient path toward innovation by managing the structural dynamics of the SBN, its network boundaries and digital platforms.

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Figure 3. Multi-level vertical and horizontal interconnected perspectives (Source: Eoh-for-Good)

The lower level consists of individuals and disconnected helices and organisations. Currently, many living labs function as isolated nodes, linking people for activities such as innovation in fab labs with 3D printers and city labs, but they lack integration. Local and sub-local innovations and collaborations also tend to be isolated. However, there is a growing push at the EU level to enhance living labs from the policy level, recognising them as spaces capable of boosting bottom-level collaboration connecting people, innovations, and helices. Incorporating initiatives like European projects or networks can further advance transformative governance.

The top-down level includes policies and strategies that enable the implementation of plans, programs, and instruments at all levels, connecting them vertically. As stated in the 2022 IPCC report: integrated, multi-sectoral, inclusive, and systems-oriented solutions, along with supportive public policies, strengthen long-term resilience (high confidence) (IPCC, 2022:90).

By bringing together diverse actors and stakeholders, co-creative multi-i tornado (as portrayed in the left-hand side of figure X) become hubs of innovation, generating transformative solutions to complex problems faced by entrepreneurs, teams, organisations, and ecosystems (Caro-González, 2023:73). The base of the vortex rotates under optimal conditions provided by the inception of ideas, intra- and entrepreneurial activities, stakeholder engagement and continuous learning and adaptation. These conditions foster knowledge exchange, experimentation, and the collective development of innovative solutions, positioning these spaces as the

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rotating bezel accelerating the needed process of change. This rotation ensures alignment, collaboration, shared ownership, continuous improvement, and resilience amidst change. The funnel expands rapidly by drawing in innovation from its edges, including interdisciplinary collaborations, local or international intersectoral projects and community-based urban and peri-urban environmentally friendly initiatives.

Innovative spaces, tools, and dynamics for purpose-driven and future-ready resilient and regenerative urban and peri-urban settlements

'In connecting the dots, it is crucial to understand what works but more important it is what did not work across different contexts' (I9-NO, 2024; 0:07:24).

The acceleration required for climate change mitigation and adaptation in cities demands a significant increase in their capacity to rapidly transform key sectors. Focus areas for targeted efforts include rooftop photovoltaic systems, electric supply, urban forestry and improving the quality of mobility.

This section explores the importance of identifying and employing both existing and new collaborative spaces and dynamics in innovative ways. Experts interviewed highlighted this as a crucial factor in accelerating regenerative climate change. We reviewed trends with experts in formal and informal place-making for climate transition in urban, peri-urban, and rural-urban areas. These initiatives represent socially driven approaches to climate transition, underlying shared responsibility for the regions where they are implemented, as discussed in the previous section.

One of today's major environmental challenges is the use of space (land, buildings, oceans, etc.) for the deployment of renewable energies (Delgado-Jiménez, 2024). However, this issue is often only dealt with on a large scale and quantitatively and not qualitatively and poorly grounded in the urban and territorial reality. Energy policies do not always consider places and their creation, where society is at the centre.

The informal construction of places, based on bottom-up actions from communities, has a key role to play to make this transition in a fair and environmentally responsible way.

To enable individuals to work together effectively, it is essential to implement spaces, mechanisms, and dynamics that both accelerate innovation and promote collaboration. This requires diverse types of living labs, community participation platforms and collaborative initiatives aimed at exchanging knowledge, ideas, practices, lessons learned, raising awareness, or influencing public policies. These mechanisms can speed up processes by involving key agents who form a coalition of

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the willing (I17- PHL, 2024)—people who share the same enthusiasm or identify with a purpose and are driven by a specific theme or problem.

The last decades have witnessed the proliferation of living labs: living labs, fab labs, collaboratories, superlabs, policy labs and other “labs” are trying to change the innovation ecosystems as an important part of our social fabric. “The Lab” could be a term that symbolises all these dispersed and unconnected pieces of a new social structure, which can be classified by:

- a) **focus area** with living labs addressing a wide range of issues, from urban mobility and sustainable urban development in Urban Living Labs, to agricultural innovation and rural development in Rural Living Labs. Health and Wellbeing Living Labs focus on digital health and elderly care, while Environmental Living Labs tackle climate change mitigation and water management. Energy Living Labs concentrate on renewable energy and energy efficiency and ICT and Digital Innovation Living Labs advance technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT) and cybersecurity. Social Innovation Living Labs promote social inclusion and community development, whereas Cultural and Creative Living Labs support the digital culture and creative industries. Educational Living Labs foster EdTech, and lifelong learning, Transport and Logistics Living Labs innovate smart transportation and Manufacturing Living Labs advance Industry 4.0. Food and Agriculture Living Labs ensure food security and sustainable farming.
- b) **geographic scope** referring to the geographic reach of living labs. Local Living Labs focus on city or community levels, while Regional Living Labs cover multiple localities. National Living Labs engage actors at the country level and International Living Labs operate across borders, involving multiple nations.
- c) **operational models** which vary from university-based living labs, corporate Living Labs, government-led living labs, community living labs, to public-private partnerships.

In addition to the ones explained by Kern (2019), several other types of instruments and dynamics facilitate collaborations in the context of polycentric and multi-level climate governance. One example are the urban living labs, designed to promote collaboration among diverse actors and, through their experimental sites, are recognised for their contribution to long-term sustainability transitions. They play a crucial role in the co-creation process, involving multiple stakeholders in developing and testing new strategies, agendas and actions aimed at creating sustainable cities. Test beds and living labs also represent an experimental, co-creative approach to innovation policy that aims to test, demonstrate and advance new sociotechnical

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arrangements and associated modes of governance in a model environment under real-world conditions (Puerari et al., 2018; Engels et al., 2019). Moreover, authors like Prats (2019) highlight the role of public-private partnerships, “as instruments to enhance the scope and efficiency of public investment by integrating the design, financing, construction, operation and maintenance phases of an infrastructure project”. There are also other climate action and multi-stakeholder platforms and networks, aiming at connecting agents to facilitate dialogue and implement joint climate initiatives (Betsill & Bulkeley, 2021).

These dimensions and models illustrate the diverse origins supporting these bottom-up initiatives that link innovators across various contexts (communities, cities, regions, territories). They respond to diverse needs and align processes, interests, and rhythms around shared or negotiated purposes, such as energy sustainability interventions within urban buildings (e.g. Sunthalpy efficiency solutions).

The multi-helix model (e.g., quadruple or n-helix) expands collaborative spaces and initiatives by including multiple sectors (government, industry, academia, and civil society) in the governance process. This promotes innovation and systemic transformation by leveraging the unique strengths and contributions of each type of actor. Living labs, which operate on the quadruple, quintuple, or n-helix models, provide scenarios for rapid co-design, co-creation, experiment, learn and upscaling urban and peri-urban positive environmental solutions in real-time.

In most interviews, the lack of proper spaces for collaboration is frequently mentioned as a key factor for identifying problems, sharing the responsibility, and enhancing an orchestrated approach for finding solutions (19-NO, 2024), (16-GER, 2024), (17-PL, 2024) & (18-ES, 2024). As one interviewee pointed out:

‘In the realm of environmental sustainability, it is evident that many initiatives struggle to engage the right audience because the necessary platforms or venues for effective outreach are lacking. The issue is not that the message does not reach anyone, but rather that it fails to reach the specific audience that needs to make impactful decisions’ [Translated in Spanish] (12-CL, 2024; 00:05:16).

Various organisations, such as museums, transnational networks and living labs, serve as essential mediating spaces for multi-level and multi-helix collaboration. These entities play a pivotal role in facilitating knowledge exchange and fostering partnerships among diverse stakeholders. By enabling innovative solutions and promoting shared responsibility across sectors and governance levels, they significantly contribute to the acceleration of positive climate change.

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Museums, for example, are particularly effective in connecting with the public and helping other sectors understand community needs and behaviours. Their role as mediators extends beyond their immediate function, influencing broader societal engagement and the mediation must be professional and neutral:

*'If I think on museums, then the strong point that I find is that they are close to people in my point of view. So this is the perspective but we are able to help the other helices, understand how to work with people, what their needs are, how they use some things so I can see that our museum is quite a lot like this **mediator** in this sense for other areas' (I3-EE, 2024; 1:10:44).*

Transnational networks and alliances are also crucial for the success of climate initiatives, offering opportunities for international cooperation and open, disruptive, or user-driven innovation.

'So, this vision of forming transnational alliances and networks is crucial for the success of these kinds of initiatives. We hope that we can effectively manage these opportunities in a positive way [Translated from Spanish] (I5-MX, 2024; 0:16:34)

'Let's say to innovate as a society by creating spaces that democratise innovation and creativity, allowing everyone to redesign their own lives and their cities' [Translated from Spanish] (I5-MX, 2024; 00:08:36)

Similarly, living labs provide multi-sectoral, multipurpose platforms that underline altruism and the common good, building value for cities, the environment, and the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

'Multi sectoral, multipurpose tools like the living labs allow to select people doing the right things and be a crucial aspect for the common good not immediate being a stakeholder with stake specifically for their own existence and self-interest. Is the altruistic aspect of living labs that need to be emphasised. To build value for the city, environment, and SDGs' (I14-CH, 2024; 1,16'06").

These collaborative spaces often involve multiple stakeholders boosting dynamics of working together (e.g. vocational educational training, social services, small businesses, public sport centres, etc.) to define the issues at hand and then jointly develop strategies to address them. This is well portrayed in one of the cases analysed which aligns the vocational training of individuals with intellectual disabilities with their empowerment as individuals, their integration into the workforce, more sustainable urban mobility, healthy lifestyles, and urban environmental care. This is achieved through the development of holistic solutions that address interconnected needs as

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explained in the novel initiative that many municipalities have overlooked.

A good example is the concept of inclusive bicycles for children and young people with special needs:

"Something that no one had thought of was making inclusive bicycles for kids who can't get on regular bikes due to special needs; they need more stability and hence a tricycle. While municipalities have implemented electric bicycles to decongest traffic and promote healthy transportation, they have not considered those who cannot use them" (I7-ES, 2024, 1:06:34).

By engaging diverse perspectives, participants can pool their expertise, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges and a greater commitment to implementing effective solutions. This approach not only enhances the quality of the outcomes but also fosters a sense of collective ownership and accountability among those involved.

These innovative spaces also provide opportunities to address ecological disasters and promote social innovation through private initiatives, as pointed out by one interviewee:

Specifically, here, for example, near Riverside, there are cases of terrible ecological disasters that have affected many indigenous populations, so we need to decide who to work with and why, and how, without participating in any form of greenwashing. However, there are many companies, like Microsoft, that are trying to generate programs promoting social innovation within their companies, enabling ecosystems for business. Microsoft, for instance, is enabling its labs and courses like TEALS or TechSpark and a variety of programmes that facilitate access to technologies' [Translated from Spanish] (I12-MX, 2024, 00:00:00).

These initiatives highlight the importance of the private sector involvement in driving regenerative climate change and the potential for businesses to act as catalysts for social and environmental innovation.

The transboundary nature of many climate change risks and species responses will require transboundary solutions through multi-national or regional governance processes on land (IPCC, 2022:111).

This is the reason to apply the multi-i model. Why is it called multi-i?

Because it unfolds combinations of collaborative dynamics with several dimensions

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that start with 'i': interpersonal, intersectional, interdisciplinary, interhelix, intersectoral, intergenerational, intercultural, inter-institutional, inter-regional and international (Caro-Gonzalez, 2023: 59-73). These interactions foster innovative co-creation and collaboration processes within and across institutions, sectors, and contexts. These approaches ensure that solutions are context-specific, socially inclusive and can become more broadly supported.

The multi-i transformative governance for innovation, involves active engagement and alignment of relevant parties, including internal and external partners, ensuring collaboration and shared ownership of the change process. Eoh-Labs and capacity-building initiatives operate alongside our interdisciplinary action-research collaborative methodology, which is rooted in a human-centred approach (Vrontis et al., 2020; landolo et al., 2024) and prioritises experimentation over mechanistic processes.

Transnational organisations, networks, living labs and other initiatives act as intermediary points to establish connections across different spaces and levels as will be explored further in the following section. Interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration is essential in this context. By integrating knowledge from various fields and involving citizens in decision-making, governance can become more responsive and effective in addressing the complex challenges of climate change (Degroot et al., 2021). As highlighted by the expert operating in Denmark:

'And when do we understand? What is the knot for? Well, suddenly, the one who has more experience in a subject can contribute and we all come to that agreement, and we build in an interdisciplinary way [...] when we talk about transdisciplinary it is no longer the discipline. For example, it is one thing to have engineers and sociologists and another thing to have a discussion with a citizen as the citizen will bring a completely different approach.' [Translated from Spanish] (I11-DK, 2024, 00:07:35).

New disciplines like techno-anthropology or techno-sociology are trying to blend social sciences and design (Børsen, Botin, 2013; Matus et al., 2018) to include diverse perspectives and expertise, going beyond traditional disciplinary boundaries and to create inclusive and comprehensive solutions. Having change agents trained in this hybrid subdiscipline of engineering and social sciences facilitates processes by providing a mediator who does not belong to a single discipline but can cross their boundaries. This allows them to seek agreements and new interpretations that can be accepted by all stakeholders. It also stresses the importance of understanding how climate change has shaped human history and the uncertainties in measuring its impact across different spatial and temporal scales.

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Environmental changes in cities and peri-urban settlements are moving typically slowly. One of the urgent needs is to accelerate regenerative urban and peri-urban climate action to enhance both individual and collective responsibility. As stated by one of the experts:

‘The type of acceleration that climate change mitigation and adaptation will require from cities require as a jump in the capacity of cities of moving fast and transform around few sectoral issues like rooftops pb, electric mobility and urban forest the quality of mobility’ I14-CH 1,16’06’’

For this, different experts and practitioners are advocating and implementing novel flexible, adaptable, collaborative and co-creative methodologies with capacity to promote resilient and regenerative urban environments (e.g. Use blockchain for transformative change, with the aim to create inclusive ecosystems; I10-NL 2024), (e.g. development of artificial intelligence tool capable of recognising patterns of Zapotec culture, fostering the democratisation of innovation of the indigenous culture; I5-MX 2024) and (e.g. the Eoh-Methodology multi-i transformative governance©, Caro-Gonzalez, 2023).

Employing co-creation is crucial for fostering innovation and sustainability, as it facilitates discussions and decision-making processes and broadens collaboration, engagement, and entrustment¹ of society. This approach helps in reaching strategic goals and making citizen engagement a goal. The critical point here, which makes companies like Eoh-for-Good and professionals such as techno-anthropologists and well-trained change agents imperative, is that poorly guided co-creation does not work, is not sustainable or leads to short-lived agreements.

Moreover, the flexible, formal, and informal setups of co-creation within urban (or peri-urban or urban-rural settled) living labs ensure diverse participation, creating dynamic environments where long-term and short-term goals can be pursued simultaneously, promoting an inclusive and innovative urban development culture (Puerari et al., 2018). The interlinked purpose of co-creation strengthens the development of solutions and shared resources by increasing participants' sense of ownership and commitment, enhancing the likelihood of successful and sustainable outcomes. To tackle climate change in urban and peri-urban areas, we must unite all levels of governance and secure broad funding to ensure efforts are aligned and effective. As one of the experts interviewed stated, we can recognise the importance of the interrelatedness between urban, peri-urban, and rural settlements and contexts:

¹ We use the term 'entrustment' instead of 'empowerment' because the latter implies that empowering one group of the population means 'disempowering' another.

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'Here, you have an ally in anyone who wishes to contribute to the common good, particularly in the context of the numerous rural communities across Spain. These villages are the foundation upon which our cities have been built, reflecting the hard work and dedication of previous generations—our grandparents and great-grandparents. Just as these rural areas once served as vital engines of development, they now have the potential to benefit us all. The key takeaway is that by focusing on and supporting rural areas, we can address many of the pressing issues currently faced by urban centres, such as housing affordability, transportation challenges and pollution.' I13-ES (43').

Many problems are intrinsically linked and therefore, addressing rural depopulation is crucial for managing urban overpopulation.

Collaborative methodologies and co-creation involve the co-responsibility and active participation of diverse actors in the design, implementation, and evaluation of initiatives, allowing motivated individuals or 'early adopters' to become agents of change, who must have a sparring partner and proper capacity programmes. This approach aligns the needs, interests and innovations of both individuals and institutions into co-creative governance networks. It employs a novel socio-digital innovation design which transforms challenges into solutions through collaborative efforts of multiple actors.

A two-way interaction and feedback mechanism is essential for social-digital-technology-driven innovators. They need to collaborate in new spaces to find effective solutions. This approach ensures that all participants can become integrated into the entire ecosystem:

"the next step is how can you, when you are a community, working together, collective action, you create value for somebody and it is offered to the whole community" (I10-NL, 2024, 0:27:00) and "everybody who is participating, whether as a developer, or as a user, or as a founder... they can all become part of the whole ecosystem" (I10-NL, 2024; 0:16:50).

Such inclusivity ensures that solutions are not only technologically sound but also socially acceptable and widely adopted. The focus should be on creating value for the community through collective action, as noted:

"The next step is how can you, when you are a community working together with collective action, you create value for somebody and this is offered to the whole community" (I10-NL, 2024; 00:16:27).

This community-centric approach fosters resilience and adaptability, essential for addressing the dynamic challenges of climate change. Despite the need for structure and specific requirements, templates should also offer enough flexibility to encourage people to explore new research ideas and innovative solutions, allowing for creative freedom. Explore how this balance can encourage people to submit diverse and potentially pioneering proposals aligned with the triple transition's innovative goals (Rodriguez Müller et al., 2024):

'It is, in some way, excluding people who have not been privileged within this system due to social structures that have been imposed for centuries' [translated from Spanish] (15-MX 00:08:40)

This principle is connected to the principle of "no one left behind" and is particularly important for women, indigenous people, and minorities. Integrated, multi-sectoral solutions that address social inequities, tailor responses to climate risks and working across systems can enhance the feasibility and effectiveness of adaptation in various sectors. (IPCC, 2022:21).

Conclusions and policy recommendations: advancing multi-Actor, multi-Level, and multi-helix collaborative governance through next-generation T-Shaped living labs

Addressing environmental challenges in urban, peri-urban, and rural settlements often progresses slowly, necessitating coordinated and aligned action across multiple factors and initiatives. Without such synchronisation, efforts to resolve environmental problems may lack the necessary pace, impact, and efficiency. This study highlights the potential of the T-Shaped concept (Shabnam et al., 2016) as a framework for enhancing multi-level transformative governance. The T-Shaped model, characterised by deep expertise in specific areas (the vertical bar of the "T") and the ability to collaborate across disciplines (the horizontal bar), is particularly effective in accelerating positive climate transitions. By integrating specialised knowledge with cross-sectoral collaboration, this model fosters comprehensive and coordinated efforts essential for addressing complex climate challenges.

To enhance responsiveness, accountability and adaptability in climate governance, this study proposes the development of a new generation of T-Shaped living labs, encompassing quadruple, quintuple, or n-helix models. These labs serve as neutral and inclusive environments for co-creation and experimentation, supporting the development of innovative solutions and policy strategies to address complex societal challenges. T-shaped living labs are collaborative spaces designed to integrate deep

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expertise in specific areas (the vertical axis) with broad, interdisciplinary collaboration (the horizontal axis). These labs foster innovation by bringing together diverse stakeholders to co-create solutions for complex challenges, such as climate change, through a balanced approach that combines specialised knowledge with cross-sectoral engagement.

T-Shaped living labs ensure that solutions are contextually relevant and meet real-world needs by promoting collaboration, learning and the integration of multiple actors in the innovation process. Moreover, they offer mechanisms for evaluating the impacts of policies and initiatives, ensuring that governance structures remain adaptable and impactful. These labs, as cooperative instruments, underscores a peer-to-peer approach between business, social and technology-driven innovations (Caro-Gonzalez, 2023).

The systemic perspective represented by the horizontal line of the T is crucial for analysing and understanding contextual factors within these settings through a holistic approach. This approach considers long-term visions, identified needs, immediate responses and shared or negotiated agendas, leading to inclusive, win-win collaborative dynamics that yield mutually beneficial outcomes.

Figure 4. New generation of T-Shaped living labs (Eoh-for-Good®)

Analysis of existing initiatives suggests that T-Shaped living labs should be founded on several underlying principles, including "leave no one behind," "inclusion and diversity," "from ego-centric to eco-centric approaches," and the "no harm principle" (Caro-Gonzalez, 2024:36-40). Additionally, the T-Model deepens vertically along several lines, such as:

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1. Communities engaging diverse individuals and organisations.
2. Context-driven connecting local and global agendas in a hyper-globalised world.
3. Fields or related sectors addressing the acceleration of climate transition.
4. Helices integrating multiple stakeholders in the innovation process.

The diverse and representative sample in this study ensures a comprehensive perspective on the varied strategies and practices employed in different urban and rural contexts. By capturing detailed narratives and in-depth insights, this research contributes valuable knowledge to the field of climate change governance and innovation, laying the groundwork for more effective and inclusive approaches to fostering positive environmental outcomes on a global scale.

The emergence of T-Shaped living labs represents a new generation of decentralised governance models that could serve as critical bridging spaces for co-creating negotiated solutions. These models enhance multi-level and multi-actor engagement by integrating multi-helix dynamics to promote initiatives for the common good. Such spaces are particularly relevant for accelerating the climate transition, shifting from destructive patterns towards regenerative ones.

There is also a pressing need for more coordinated co-creation efforts and the international exchange of examples of radical action. Developing new policies and measures that achieve broader political acceptance should be underlined. Active engagement of citizens and diverse actors is crucial for the success of transformative governance. Policymakers should prioritise mechanisms that facilitate inclusive participation, such as public consultations, participatory budgeting, and collaborative platforms. These approaches help foster a sense of ownership and co-responsibility, driving sustained and collective action toward accelerating positive climate change.

Addressing climate change in cities and peri-urban and rural areas requires a comprehensive analysis that acknowledges the interconnectedness of these issues with others.

For example, tackling urban overpopulation should involve efforts to reverse rural depopulation, addressing two critical issues simultaneously for more effective solutions. Urban and rural environments are interdependent, with cities relying on rural areas for raw materials and rural regions depending on urban centers for services and products.

Another critical consideration is the unique conditions of each city or location where an initiative is to be implemented. While this may seem obvious, it is essential to

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recognize that every cities or peri-urban settlement's circumstances, context and challenges are distinct, with local culture and character playing significant roles. Decision-making processes must be tailored to the specific needs of each location, as strategies that succeed in one city may not necessarily be effective elsewhere. Involving all relevant stakeholders in the decision-making process is crucial to ensuring co-responsibility and practical, beneficial outcomes. This approach aligns with the quintuple helix model, which engages a broad range of actors—from citizens to businesses—in the planning and implementation of solutions.

In conclusion, addressing and accelerating regenerative climate change in urban, peri-urban, and rural areas necessitates a multifaceted strategy that integrates innovative transformative governance, individual and collective responsibility among societal actors and the design and implementation of new frameworks for innovation, such as T-Shaped living labs.

This study underscores the importance of incorporating expert perspectives, which confirm the advantages of this new generation of living labs. These labs must clearly promote principles of interdisciplinarity and rigour to specialise knowledge and develop effective, inclusive, and sustainable solutions. We can create impactful strategies to mitigate the anthropogenic effects of climate change and drive positive environmental outcomes by fostering well-trained agents of change, interdisciplinary collaboration, engaging all stakeholders and leveraging these advanced living labs.

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